

CLIMATE CHANGE AND INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION: A CRITIQUE OF NIGERIA'S COMMITMENTS, 1972-2024

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Abstract

This paper examined climate change and international cooperation: a critique of Nigeria's commitments, 1972-2024. Climate change poses a significant global challenge that societies worldwide are striving to mitigate. This paper examines Nigeria's role in international climate agreements. It traces global climate action efforts beginning with the Stockholm Earth Summit and explores Nigeria's commitments to reducing emissions and expanding renewable energy. The paper highlights Nigeria's progress, including the expansion of green and renewable energy, while also addressing policy and institutional challenges. It suggests ways to strengthen institutional frameworks by promoting economic diversification. Furthermore, the paper critiques Nigeria's role in global agreements, acknowledging challenges such as inadequate funding and the inefficient use of funds received from international donors. The research employed a historical qualitative objective analysis of primary and secondary sources. Findings reveal that Nigeria's commitments to global climate efforts are often more rhetorical than practical. The paper concludes by advocating for tangible commitments from Nigeria by ensuring the effective utilization of international donor funds to combat climate change and encouraging policies and actions that will lead to transition to green energy.

Keywords: Climate Change, International, Cooperation, Agreements.

Introduction

Climate change poses a significant threat to Nigeria in particular and to the global community at large. Nigeria is already experiencing the severe consequences of climate change. Climate Change could be described as long-term alterations in the average weather patterns and temperatures on earth. These changes can occur naturally due to factors such as volcanic eruptions, variations in solar radiation, and natural shifts in the earth's orbit. However, in the recent times, it has been primarily driven by human activities, particularly burning of fossil fuels, deforestation, industrial activities, agriculture, etc. These changes have a profound impact on various aspects of life, affecting farmlands, homes, water sources, food crops, trees, animals, and human health. The increasing frequency of extreme weather events, such as floods, heat waves, and droughts, highlights the urgency for global collaboration to mitigate its effects.¹

Over the past few years, Nigeria's climate has exhibited noticeable irregularities. Extreme weather patterns, including prolonged dry spells and intense rainfall, have become more frequent. Rising temperatures, sea levels, and instances of flooding,

drought, desertification, and land degradation are further exacerbating the situation. These changes have a significant impact on freshwater resources and have led to a loss of biodiversity and arable lands. For Nigeria, the stakes are obviously high. As Africa's most populous nation and largest oil producer, the country is both a contributor to and victim of climate change. As a result of these, Nigeria faces severe challenges. For instance, rising temperatures (average annual temperatures have risen by 1.1°C) since 1960, exacerbating heatwaves and reducing agricultural productivity.² Desertification in Northern regions have resulted in the lost of lands which is threatening food security and livelihoods, and flooding in coastal cities like Lagos experience which have continued to have severe flooding due to rising sea levels and inadequate drainage systems, displacing millions annually.³ A climate challenging situation like this is such the Nigeria cannot tackle alone but requires international cooperation.

International cooperation refers to the relationships established among the peoples and nations of the world, aimed at addressing existential challenges and achieving common goals for humanity. It involves the exchange of knowledge, financial resources, and collaborative mechanisms to overcome barriers such as poor governance, lack of capital, and climate change. The need for unified action and the desire of nations to maintain relevance on the global stage make international cooperation both necessary and indispensable. Nigeria's participation in international collaboration demonstrates its acknowledgment of these threats and commitment for solution. However, aligning international commitments with domestic realities remains a complex challenge. Factors such as reliance on oil revenues, limited resources, and socio-economic inequalities hinder the implementation of effective climate policies.

Climate change has emerged as a prominent issue of discourse across local, national, and international platforms. Although substantial scholarly work has addressed various aspects of the phenomenon, however, this paper aims to explore dimensions that remain under examined. In line with this objective, it critically assesses Nigeria's commitments within the framework of global climate change agreements. Against this backdrop, the current discussion revolved around the following sub-themes: Historical timeline on worlds Efforts to Combat Climate Change; Nigeria's Commitments in Global Climate agreements; Progress on Nigeria's climate commitments; Critique of Nigeria's role in Global agreements; Economic dependencies and contradictions; and Opportunities for improvement on Nigeria's international commitments

Historical Timeline on Worlds Effort to Combat Climate Change

The journey to address climate change began in Stockholm, Sweden, from June 5 to 16, 1972, during the UN Scientific Conference, also known as the First Earth Summit. This conference adopted a declaration outlining principles for preserving and enhancing the human environment and included an action plan with recommendations for international environmental action. For the first time, the Declaration raised the issue of climate change, urging governments to be mindful of activities that could lead to climate change and to evaluate the likelihood and magnitude of its effects.⁴

In 1988, global warming and ozone layer depletion gained prominence in public debates and political agendas. The UN General Assembly recognized climate change as a critical issue, urging UNEP and WMO to conduct a comprehensive

review and propose strategies to mitigate its impact. This led to the establishment of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) and the adoption of significant measures in 1989, including preparations for a framework convention on climate change and regional initiatives like the Malé Declaration on Global Warming and Sea Level Rise. The Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer also entered into force in 1989, marking a milestone in environmental action. Further progress was achieved at the second World Climate Conference in 1990, where a Ministerial Declaration called for immediate negotiations on a climate framework convention. This momentum culminated in the 1992 Earth Summit in Rio de Janeiro, which produced the Rio Declaration and Agenda 21. Chapter 9 of Agenda 21 highlighted the links between science, sustainable development, energy, transportation, and industrial practices in protecting the atmosphere.⁵

The most significant outcome of the Earth Summit was the opening for signature of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), aimed at stabilizing greenhouse gas concentrations to prevent dangerous interference with the climate system. By 1992, 158 states had signed the Convention, which entered into force in 1994. The Berlin Mandate of 1995 launched talks for stronger commitments from developed nations, culminating in the Kyoto Protocol in 1997. The Protocol required industrialized countries to reduce emissions by at least 5% below 1990 levels between 2008 and 2012. Signed in 1998, it became effective in 2005, solidifying global efforts to combat climate change.⁶ Another significant milestone in this regard is the Paris Agreement, an international treaty on climate change negotiated by 196 parties during the 2015 United Nations Climate Change Conference in Paris. It was signed in 2016 and entered into force that same year.⁷

A key development following the Paris Agreement was the Glasgow Climate Pact of 2021. The UN Climate Change Conference held in Glasgow (COP26) convened 120 world leaders and over 40,000 registered participants, including 22,274 party delegates, 14,124 observers, and 3,886 media representatives. However, the outcome of the conference drew mixed reactions. UN Secretary-General António Guterres expressed disappointment, stating:

The approved texts are a compromise. They reflect the interests, the conditions, the contradictions, and the state of political will in the world today. They take important steps, but unfortunately, the collective political will was not enough to overcome some deep contradictions.⁸

Nigeria's Commitments in Global Climate Agreements

Nigeria has shown some level of commitment to addressing climate change. This is evident in its Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) under the Paris Agreement, which set ambitious goals to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions and transition to a more sustainable economy. Since the coming together of world leaders to deliberate on ways to reduce carbon emissions in the atmosphere and mitigate the multi-dimensional and inter-related effects of climate change in the world, the global discourse on climate change has evolved around limiting temperature rise above pre-industrial levels and achieving net zero carbon emissions in the future. At COP26 in Glasgow, Nigeria committed to achieving net zero by 2060.⁹

After the Glasgow Summit, the then President Of Nigeria Muhammadu Buhari signed into law the Climate Change Act on the 18th of November, 2021. This demonstrated the commitment of Nigeria in the fight against climate change. The Act, provides an

all-inclusive, regulatory legal framework for achieving Nigeria's long-term climate goals that include net-zero carbon emissions by 2060, adequate climate financing, environmental and economic accountability. The efforts to implement the plans enshrined in the Act and Nigeria's Nationally Determined¹⁰ Contribution, including development of a carbon market framework. Efforts are on to ensure that Nigeria as a leading contributor to climate change in Africa and a leader in the fight against it, continue charging for path to achieving green growth and sustainable economic development. Nigeria aims to achieve a 20% unconditional reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by 2030. This target could increase to 47% with international support through financing, technology transfer, and capacity building. These reductions focus on key sectors, including energy, agriculture, and waste management, where emissions are most significant. To reduce reliance on fossil fuels, Nigeria plans to increase the share of renewable energy to 30% of its electricity mix, emphasizing solar and wind energy.¹¹ These efforts aim to provide cleaner, more reliable energy sources while addressing energy access challenges in rural and underserved areas.

Progress on Nigeria's Climate Commitments

Nigeria has made notable strides in renewable energy development and climate adaptation efforts, though significant challenges remain. Renewable energy at least in policy has become a cornerstone of Nigeria's climate strategy, reflecting the government's commitment to reducing greenhouse gas emissions and increasing energy access. Through the Solar Power Naija Program, aimed to empower over 5 million households with access to off-grid solar solutions, thus, reducing dependency on kerosene and diesel generators while providing cleaner, cost-effective alternatives.¹² The initiative not only cuts emissions but also supports rural electrification, empowering communities with reliable energy sources for economic activities. In addition to solar energy, Nigeria is gradually expanding wind and hydroelectric projects. For instance, the Katsina Wind Farm demonstrates the country's potential in harnessing wind power.¹³ Similarly, hydroelectric projects such as the Mambilla Hydroelectric Plant aim to increase renewable energy capacity. However, progress in these areas has been hindered by funding limitations, bureaucratic delays, and infrastructural challenges, underscoring the need for stronger public-private partnerships and international support.¹⁴

Given Nigeria's vulnerability to climate impacts, adaptation initiatives have been prioritized to build resilience and safeguard livelihoods. The Nigeria Erosion and Watershed Management Project (NEWMAP) is a key example, supporting over 2.6 million people in erosion-prone areas and restoring 3,000 hectares of degraded land. By addressing soil erosion and land degradation, the project enhances agricultural productivity and reduces the risk of displacement in affected communities. Flood mitigation programs are another focus, particularly in coastal cities like Lagos, which face recurrent flooding due to rising sea levels and poor drainage systems. While some flood-resilient infrastructure has been implemented, such as improved drainage networks and embankments, the scale of these efforts remains insufficient to address the magnitude of the threat. Greater investment and long-term planning are needed to protect vulnerable populations.¹⁵

While the Climate Change Act represents a significant step in improving climate governance in Nigeria. It mandates annual reviews of climate action plans, ensuring that policies remain responsive to evolving challenges. The establishment of a National Council on Climate Change provides a centralized body to oversee the implementation of climate initiatives and coordinate efforts across sectors. However,

enforcement remains a critical challenge. Inadequate funding, limited technical capacity, and weak institutional frameworks hinder the full realization of the Act's potential. Without robust mechanisms to monitor and enforce compliance, progress could be slow. While Nigeria has made commendable progress in renewable energy development, adaptation efforts, and policy formulation, substantial gaps remain. Achieving its climate goals will require a multifaceted approach, including increased investment, capacity building, and enhanced international collaboration.¹⁶ If concrete efforts are made to addressing these challenges, Nigeria can in reality be seen as a leader in climate action within Africa, ensuring sustainable development for future generations.

A Critique of Nigeria's Role in Global Agreements

Nigeria's participation in global climate agreements, while commendable, is fraught with challenges that undermine its ability to meet international commitments. These challenges span policy frameworks, economic dependencies, access to climate finance, and public engagement.

*Policy and Institutional Challenges:*One of the major hurdles in Nigeria's climate efforts is institutional fragmentation. Multiple agencies, such as the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) and the Federal Ministry of Environment, often have overlapping mandates. This redundancy creates inefficiencies, delays, and confusion, ultimately weakening the implementation of climate policies. Additionally, while Nigeria's policies under frameworks like the Paris Agreement are ambitious, they frequently lack clear roadmaps, monitoring, and evaluation mechanisms. For instance, while the Climate Change Act of 2021 is a significant milestone, its enforcement remains inconsistent due to weak institutional structures and inadequate funding. Without well-defined implementation strategies, Nigeria risks falling short of its targets in its commitment on climate change

*Economic Dependencies and Contradictions:*Nigeria's heavy reliance on oil revenue presents a stark contradiction to its climate commitments. With oil contributing approximately 85% of export earnings and 50% of government revenue,¹⁷ the economy remains tethered to fossil fuels, a major source of greenhouse gas emissions. Efforts to transition to renewable energy and diversify into sustainable sectors are hindered by underfunding and slow progress. While renewable energy initiatives like the Solar Power Naija Program are promising, they represent only a fraction of the investment needed to significantly reduce dependence on fossil fuels. The lack of a cohesive strategy to balance economic growth with emissions reductions highlights a disconnection between national priorities and climate objectives.

*Access to Climate Finance:*Nigeria has struggled to fully leverage international climate finance mechanisms, such as the Green Climate Fund (GCF). Although eligible for these funds, bureaucratic inefficiencies and a lack of institutional capacity to develop bankable projects limit access. Many proposed initiatives fail to meet the rigorous standards required for funding approval, leaving critical adaptation and mitigation projects underfunded. Furthermore, the slow pace of disbursement and the complexity of application processes deter many local governments and private entities from seeking international funding. Addressing these barriers is essential to unlocking the financial resources needed to implement large-scale climate solutions.¹⁸

*Public Awareness and Stakeholder Engagement:*Public awareness of climate change and its impacts remains low in Nigeria, particularly at the grassroots level.¹⁹ Limited understanding of climate issues reduces public participation in environmental initiatives, weakening the collective effort needed to achieve national goals. Community involvement is vital for the success of adaptation projects, such as erosion control and flood mitigation, yet such engagement is often minimal. The private sector's role in climate action is also underdeveloped. While private investment in green technologies could significantly boost progress, the lack of strong incentives, such as tax breaks or subsidies, deters meaningful involvement. Establishing a more enabling environment for private sector participation is critical for scaling up renewable energy and other sustainable ventures.²⁰

Furthermore, many policy declarations are mere facades, lacking genuine implementation. For example, while solar energy could significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions, it remains prohibitively expensive for most Nigerians. As a result, the majority still rely on generators and firewood to meet their energy needs. Another glaring issue is the widespread use of motor tires for roasting cows in major markets, a practice that contributes to environmental pollution.²¹ This lack of commitment is reflected in the 2021 Notre Dame Global Adaptation Index, which ranks Nigeria as the 53rd most vulnerable and 6th least-prepared country globally to adapt to climate change.²² It could be argued given the short period of this global threat that much commitment should not be expected from Nigeria in terms of commitment. To a reasonable extent such an argument in its face value could be adjudged valid. However, looking at the existing threats posed by climate change such an argument may be found wanting. Even though much is not expected from Nigeria, it is expected that Nigeria ought to have taken some concrete steps beyond the stage of theory and rhetoric. For instance, in the area renewable energy which the citizens of Nigeria could be encouraged to transit to is frost with challenges deliberately made by the government to the people from accessing it as they view such transition moves not good for an economy that is dependent on fossil fuel.

Opportunities for Improvement on Nigeria's International Commitments

Nigeria has significant opportunities to strengthen its role in addressing climate change and fulfilling its commitments under global agreements. These opportunities span institutional capacity, economic diversification, access to climate finance, and engagement with public and private sectors.

*Strengthening Institutional Capacity:*One of the key steps toward improving Nigeria's climate action is establishing a centralized body dedicated to overseeing climate governance. While the Climate Change Act (2021) mandates the creation of a National Council on Climate Change, ensuring that this body is empowered, well-funded, and equipped with qualified personnel is crucial. A centralized authority can streamline coordination among agencies, reduce redundancies, and ensure a unified approach to implementing climate policies. Additionally, developing a robust monitoring and evaluation framework is essential. Such a framework would enable the government to track emissions reductions, assess the effectiveness of climate projects, and make data-driven adjustments.

*Economic Diversification:*Reducing Nigeria's economic reliance on fossil fuels is critical to aligning its development with climate goals. Accelerating investments in renewable energy, particularly solar and wind, offers a viable pathway for diversification. Programs like the Solar Power Naija initiative have demonstrated the potential for renewable energy to drive economic growth while reducing emissions.

Expanding these programs and encouraging partnerships with international investors can further unlock Nigeria's renewable energy potential. Climate-smart agriculture is another avenue for diversification. By adopting sustainable farming practices, such as agroforestry, improved irrigation systems, and soil conservation techniques, Nigeria can enhance food security while reducing emissions. These practices also have the potential to improve rural livelihoods, creating a more resilient agricultural sector in the face of climate change.

*Accessing Climate Finance:*Unlocking climate finance remains a critical opportunity for Nigeria to scale up its adaptation and mitigation efforts. This could also be made is by building the capacity of government agencies and local organizations to design and implement bankable projects is key to accessing mechanisms like the Green Climate Fund (GCF). This involves training personnel, simplifying application processes, and fostering collaboration with international development partners. Bureaucratic barriers that hinder fund access must also be addressed. Streamlining approval processes and creating a clear, transparent framework for managing climate finance will not only attract more funding but also build trust among donors and investors. Establishing regional climate finance hubs could further enhance accessibility, particularly for local governments and community-based organizations.²³

*Public and Private Sector Engagement:*Increasing public awareness of climate issues is vital for fostering grassroots participation and support for climate initiatives. Nationwide education campaigns, using media platforms and community outreach programs, can help citizens understand the importance of climate action and how they can contribute. Schools, religious organizations, and local leaders can play critical roles in amplifying these messages. The private sector also has a pivotal role in driving Nigeria's climate agenda. Providing tax incentives, subsidies, and other financial benefits can encourage businesses to invest in renewable energy, sustainable infrastructure, and green technologies. Public-private partnerships (PPPs) should be actively pursued to mobilize resources and expertise for large-scale projects, such as renewable energy installations and climate-resilient urban planning.²⁴

Nigeria's climate challenges are significant, but so are the opportunities to improve its climate governance and implementation. It is up Nigeria to strengthened institutional capacity, diversify the economy, improve access to climate finance, and foster engagement with the public and private sectors. These are crucial steps toward achieving national and international climate goals. Addressing these areas, Nigeria can transition to a more sustainable and resilient economy while fulfilling its global commitments. Success will depend on sustained political will, strategic partnerships, and the active involvement of all stakeholders, from policymakers and private companies to local communities and international organizations. Embracing these opportunities will not only mitigate the impacts of climate change but also position Nigeria as a model for climate leadership in Africa and beyond.

Conclusion

This paper critiqued Nigeria's role in international climate agreements from 1972 to 2024. It explored Nigeria's commitments to global efforts, including emission reduction and renewable energy expansion, highlighting progress in adopting green and renewable energy initiatives. However, the study identified significant policy and institutional challenges that hindered effective implementation. Findings also showed

that Nigeria was one of the countries that had not demonstrated sufficient readiness to combat climate change. Additionally, Nigeria's industrial activities were found to contribute significantly to climate change, further complicating its role in global mitigation efforts. Despite receiving international donor funds, Nigeria did not utilize these resources effectively to achieve tangible results. The paper concluded that Nigeria's contributions were often limited to policy declarations rather than practical actions. To improve its global standing, it was recommended that Nigeria demonstrate accountability and achieve measurable progress using available resources from international environment. It is also important to state that Nigeria has shown commitment to global climate agreements but faces significant challenges in translating these commitments into actionable results. Strengthening institutional frameworks, diversifying the economy, and improving access to climate finance are essential steps forward.

ENDNOTES

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20. The government is only interested in taxing the private sector without making any meaning commitment to enable the private sector to be part of the effort. In the fight against climate change it could best be described that Nigeria as a government is working alone.

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